

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF HIGH STRENGTH AND HIGH OIL RESISTANT FLAME RETARDANT EVA COMPOSITES FOR CABLE

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ABSTRACT

Glycidyl methacrylate grafted ethylene-octene copolymer (POE-g-GMA) was introduced into ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer (EVA)/flame retardants (FRC) composites via melt blending and hot press vulcanization method. The particle dispersion, thermal performance, rheological behavior, mechanical properties and oil resistance of the composites were studied. It was observed from SEM photographs that POE-g-GMA could reduce the occurrence of filler agglomeration and enhanced the interfacial adhesion between filler and the matrix. The rheological measurement results showed that the sample appeared the plateau in the low frequency region, illustrating the formation of filler network. Owing to the compatibilization effect of POE-g-GMA promoted the relative ordered dispersion and distribution of filler, the tensile strength of the composites was improved. In addition, the oil resistance of the composites is effectively strengthened, which is manifested by a small decrease in mechanical properties after oil immersion treatment due to the enhancement and improvement of the internal interface structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer (EVA) is one of the commonly used polymer matrix in cable industry owing to its excellent barrier properties, low temperature toughness, stress crack resistance and weather resistance^[1-5]. It is mostly used as the sheath or insulation material for wire and cable, especially in the field of high-speed trains and urban rail transit. However, its large-scale application is seriously restricted by the characteristics of flammability, which is widely found in the majority of polymer materials. In order to overcome this kind of drawback, it is generally carried out by using inorganic hydroxide such as magnesium hydroxide (MH) and aluminum hydroxide (ATH) to implement flame retardant modification.

It is similar to the vast majority of fillers, this flame retardant has certain impact on the performance of the composites. The introduction of the high concentration flame retardants always cause a decrease in mechanical properties, which results in a relatively high polarity and poor affinity with most polymer matrix. The full potential of performance of the composites is only realized when fillers are homogeneously dispersed within the matrix and the strong interfacial bonding between the filler and polymer matrix is obtained^[7-9].

Until now, many studies have been conducted in-depth and systematically on the above problems. By modifying the flame retardant to change the physical or chemical state of its surface, it is possible to achieve the better compatibility between filler and polymer, which can improve the flame retardancy as well as the mechanical properties, flexibility and thermal stability. Chen et al. carried out an experiment using Mg(OH)₂ modified with zinc stearate and titanate, as filler in polypropylene (PP), the results showed a better distribution of particles of Mg(OH)₂ after the addition of the titanate and stearate, directly improving their compatibility, and thereby also the mechanical properties of the PP/Mg(OH)₂ composite^[10]. Silane coupling agent is an effective surface treatment agent and has been adopted for a long time in actual industrial production^[11]. Wang demonstrated that modified Mg(OH)₂/siloxane nanocomposites obtained using the hydrothermal and hypergravity method had potential flame retarding properties^[12]. The observation exhibited that the surface area of the composite particles was reduced, and the affinity and thermal stability were both improved. Studies to

date have not produced measurable effects, however, and the properties of the materials being obtained are still far from optimum.

Although plenty of studies have obtained truer results, still cannot be tightly integrated with the actual application. As for the way in which the filler achieves good dispersion, and the driving force of its good interface with the polymer, is not clearly explained. In this paper, industrial grade magnesium hydroxide together with aluminum hydroxide as flame retardants to fill the EVA matrix with glycidyl methacrylate grafted ethylene-octene copolymer (POE-*g*-GMA) as macromolecular compatibilizer. The influences of POE-*g*-GMA on morphology, crystallization behavior and rheological property were detailly investigated. As a composite material that equip cables, its related performance has also been tested.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

EVA, POE-*g*-GMA, MH, ATH and various processing aids were mixed on an open two-roll mill with the temperature of 100 °C for 10 min. After that, crosslinking agent dicumyl peroxide (DCP) and crosslinking coagent triallylisocyanurate (TAIC) were added into, continue to homogenize for 5 min. At last, the mixing compound was molded by hot-pressing at 170 °C and 10 MPa for 20 min.

Fig.1 The structure of POE-*g*-GMA.

The morphology of tensile fracture surface was observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-6490LV) at a 20 kV accelerating voltage. The thermal stability of EVA/POE-*g*-GMA/GMA composites were studied by thermogravimetric analyzer (Q500, TA instruments). Tests were performed from ambient temperature to 800°C under nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The Non-isothermal crystallization behavior of the composites was investigated by differential scanning calorimeter (Q2000, TA instruments) with N₂ as the purging gas. The samples were cooled to -40 °C at 10 °C/min after eliminating the heat history, and then heat from -40 °C to 200 °C at the same rate. Viscoelastic properties were measured using a rheometrics mechanical spectrometer (RMS800). Measurements were performed in oscillatory shear at a fixed temperature of 150 °C with the frequency changed from 0.05 rad/s to 500 rad/s. The mechanical properties were tested according to IEC 60811-1-1. The sample size was 5A and the tensile rate was 200 mm/min. The oil resistance was tested by following IEC 60811-2-1. The medium is IRM903 fuel oil.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effects of POE-*g*-GMA on microstructure of EVA composites

Fig.2 shows the microscopic images of representative fracture surface of different samples. It is obvious that the overall damage widely distributed throughout the field in the absence of POE-*g*-GMA, even a large number of holes and continuous strips. In addition, the particles not only have a smooth surface, but also have a clear interface with the matrix. These observations indicate the formation of particle agglomeration and weak interface binding force of polymer-particle. As POE-*g*-GMA loading increases, although layered sections still exist, the fracture areas become rougher with the holes have declined in number and size compared with the blank. Together, it is immediately apparent that a certain degree of threading occurs (as shown in the red circle). At the same time, there are some particles embedded inside the polymer matrix and the interface between the two is blurred, especially with introduction of 7wt% of POE-*g*-GMA, demonstrating the local plastic deformation occurring

during the tensile test. The above results suggest that the agglomeration of particle is effectively restrained, its dispersibility also improved in the presence of POE-g-GMA. Accurately, this sort of macromolecule compatibilizer is beneficial to enhance the interaction between filler and matrix, and to increase the thickness of the phase interface. Therefore, the interface structure of the composite can be stabilized and strengthened.

Fig.2 The SEM images of tensile fracture surface of EVA composites.

3.2 Effects of POE-g-GMA on the non-isothermal crystallization behavior of EVA composites

The DSC thermal analytical curves were used to study the glass transition behavior of the above samples. Fig.3 shows the cooling curve after eliminated heat history. It can be seen that all samples show obvious crystallization peaks. The crystallization peak is sharp when the amount of POE-g-GMA added is 0wt%, accompanying a narrow temperature span. As the content of POE-g-GMA increases, the peak shape significantly changed, which gradually became wider and becomes dull. Apart from this, the corresponding crystallization temperature also shifts to the low temperature region. Note that EVA/3wt% POE-g-GMA/FRC and EVA/7wt% POE-g-GMA/FRC showed lower T_g of 34.23 °C and 32.96 °C, respectively, than EVA/0wt% POE-g-GMA/FRC with T_g of 35.24 °C. These results were ascribed to the weakened ordering ability of EVA molecular chain with the introduction of POE-g-GMA, which results in the difficulty of forming a macroscopic ordered structure with good regularity of the amorphous region. As a consequence, the crystallization temperature decreased and the crystallization peak was passivated. As can be clearly seen from the secondary heating curves, the above samples showed melting peaks (T_m) at around 50 °C. The temperature corresponding to this peak is negatively correlated with the compatibilizer content. When the amount of POE-g-GMA was 7wt%, the melting temperature was decreased from 51.65 °C to 49.14 °C, which is consistent with the cooling curve. It is conceivable that POE-g-GMA made the molecular chain irregularity in the amorphous region. The result is that the imperfect ordered structure was destroyed at a lower temperature during the heating process.

Fig.3 DSC cooling curves (a) and second heating curves (b) of EVA composites.

3.3 Effects of POE-g-GMA on rheology behavior of EVA composites

Viscoelastic properties of EVA/FRC composites were specifically evaluated. Fig.4(a) is the curve of storage modulus (G') versus angular frequency (ω). In the high frequency range, the storage modulus is not consistent, indicating that the high frequency viscoelasticity does not solely depend on the polymer matrix throughout the filling system. G' of samples with loading of 1wt% and 3wt% compatibilizer both exhibits higher value than that with loading of 5wt% and 7wt% in the low frequency range. It illustrates that the G' of the former two samples are more sensitive to the change of ω than the latter two. The reason is that, the cross-linking network of the matrix in the system was imperfect at a relatively low loading of compatibilizer. This type of solidlike behavior occurred in the material owing to the formation of filler network, especially when the filler content is high. And yet, the cross-linking network structure of matrix tended to be completed at a high content of compatibilizer, which made this sort of phenomenon almost disappeared. It cannot be ignored the fact that, the former two samples appeared the plateau in the low frequency region. The unusually experimental phenomenon is credited to the well-formed network of filler particle, because POE-g-GMA has the function of promoting uniform dispersion of the filler. Thus, the relationship between G' and ω obviously deviated from the classical linear viscoelastic theory. As for loss modulus, which is presented in Fig.4(b). In the low frequency region, the loss modulus of the sample having a POE-g-GMA content of 1wt% and 3wt% were found to be considerably higher than that of 5wt% and 7wt%. In general, the higher the storage modulus, the lower the loss modulus. But in the research system of this paper, the storage modulus and loss modulus of the former two were both higher. Due to the compatibilization effect of POE-g-GMA, the physical-chemical interaction between the polymer matrix and the inorganic filler was enhanced. At the same time, the internal friction between the fillers during the long-range motion of the macromolecule caused the energy to be dissipated in terms of heat as a consequence of the high proportion of filler. The result, as aspect of macroscopic, was an increase in loss modulus.

Fig.4 Storage modulus (a) and loss modulus (b) of EVA composites.

3.4 Effects of POE-g-GMA on mechanical properties of EVA composites

The tensile properties and oil resistant properties of the EVA/FRC composites containing different amounts of POE-g-GMA are presented in Table 1. It can be seen that tensile strength increases with POE-g-GMA loading, reaches the highest value of 13.9 MPa which is 2.0 MPa higher than that of the sample with no POE-g-GMA. Based on the above analysis, it can be concluded that the improvement of the mechanical properties of the composites is due to the better dispersion of flame retardant particles and stronger interfacial adhesion to the substrate because of the presence of compatibilizer. The tensile strength before and after oil immersion was measured and compared to evaluate the oil resistance of the composites. In fact, the surface of the flame retardant such as magnesium hydroxide is rich in polar hydroxyl groups, which can theoretically enhance oil resistance to some extent. The actual situation is that the addition of such flame retardants is relatively high, and the particles tend to agglomerate, resulting in difficulty in dispersion. More importantly, the instability of the organic-inorganic phase interface structure formed inside the material is caused by more internal defects.

Therefore, after the oil immersion treatment, the oil molecule easily attacks and penetrates from the interface defect, thereby causing the overall destruction of the interface. By adding a certain amount of POE-*g*-GMA, the interfacial adhesion between filler and the matrix can be significantly improved. The rheological test has proved the formation of the internal solid network, indicating that the phase interface structure tends to be perfect. According to the above facts, there is no doubt that as the compatibilizer content increases, the oil resistance of the composites is effectively strengthened, especially when adding 7% by mass of POE-*g*-GMA, the tensile strength reduction rate of the sample is only 19%.

Table 1 Tensile properties and oil resistance of EVA composites.

Sample	unit	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
T.S	MPa	11.9	12.1	12.6	13.3	13.9
E.B	%	160	165	179	162	177
change of T.S(oil)	%	-18	-19	-19	-12	-13
change of E.B(oil)	%	-15	-14	-15	-10	-9

4 CONCLUSION

Macromolecular compatibilizer POE-*g*-GMA is used to modify EVA composites. The related results showed obvious improvements in the interfacial interactions, which was attributed to the improved filler dispersion and strengthened interfacial bonding induced by POE-*g*-GMA. A modified interphase structure was accordingly proposed and related to the mechanical performance.

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